

The Chemistry of Jute-lignin. Part I. A Comparative Study of Different Methods of Isolation.

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The fundamental difference in the composition of jute and cotton, is that the ultimate lengths of single cells of jute are much less than that of cotton (about 0.6 mm. for jute and 30—40 mm. for cotton) and that these single cells are joined together by a gummy matter in the case of jute, as a result of which the fibre appears much longer. The percentage of this incrusting material is pretty high, being about 25 per cent. In fact, cotton is 98 per cent. pure cellulose, whereas jute contains only 74 per cent. The incrusting matter on the cell-walls of jute fibre consists mainly of lignin, hemi-celluloses, uronic acids and pectin. These constituents obviously modify the physical and chemical properties of the fibre to a very great extent. But the function played by each individually is not yet definitely known; neither the way in which these substances occur in the fibre, nor the relationship, if any, that exists amongst them, has been established. Thus, there exists a good deal of controversy as to the nature of existence of lignin in lingo-celluloses; some hold it to be a case of physical adsorption whilst others are of opinion that the two are chemically combined. In order to study the effects of these constituents on the properties of cellulose in the case of jute, each individual must be studied separately. Lignin is by far the most important constituent of the cell-wall, forming as it does, as much as 15 per cent. It was therefore thought advisable to study first of all this important member.

The simple ligno-cellulose typified by the annual jute forms a much more promising starting point for the study of lignin than the various woods. The low ash-content also indicates the suitability of the jute-lignin for scientific investigations.

While attempting to study a natural product, specially when it exists in conjunction with several others, the most important point that should always be borne in mind, is that it must be isolated in the least drastic way, using the mildest reagents, so that it may not

suffer any appreciable change during isolation. If this is ignored, we get not the genuine substance, but only a decomposition product, the study of which may not serve any useful purpose. It was therefore necessary to make first of all, a comparative study of the different methods of isolation of lignin, with the most recent modifications, in order to select the best one, most suitable for jute.

As the composition of jute fibre varies from sample to sample so far as these constituents are concerned, the same sample was used throughout the investigation. The middle portion of the jute was taken rejecting about 4 inches from below and one foot from above. The fibres were mechanically separated as far as possible, cut into small pieces, and the adhering foreign matter was removed first by simply washing with water several times and then by treating with neutral soap using distilled water all the while. The method of removing resin and fat by boiling with 0.5 per cent. caustic soda was rejected as it was found that a small amount of lignin was removed thereby.

In the case of timbers, Mehta (*Biochem. J.*, 1925, 19, 958) found lignin partly in the free state (from 0.32 to 22.8 per cent.) in different timbers, directly extractible by alcohol, and partly in combination with cellulose hydrolysable with alkali. Accordingly jute was extracted with alcohol (95 per cent.) in a Soxhlet for about six hours, the residue obtained from the extract amounted to only 0.87 per cent. which failed to give any test for lignin. Jute was also extracted with acetone-alcohol mixture (2:1) which is an excellent solvent for free alkali lignin, but no trace of lignin could be found in the residue obtained from the extract.

Resin and fat were removed by extracting the fairly dried jute with a mixture of alcohol-benzene (1:1); only one extraction for six hours was found to be quite sufficient. Jute thus treated was used in this investigation.

The moisture content of the fibre varied within wide limits during the year—thus in August (rainy season) the percentage of moisture was 15.75, in December (winter) it was 12.04 and in March (summer) it has been found to be 8.4 only. The usual constants were therefore calculated always on dry jute. The results of analysis of the jute used for the study of lignin are given below:

α -Cellulose ...	67.0 per cent.	Moisture ...	8.4 to 15.75 per cent.
Furfural ...	9.64 per cent	Ash ...	0.51 per cent.
Resin and fat...	0.91 per cent.	Uronic acids...	8.0 per cent,

Distribution of Lignin along the Fibre.—The lower part of the fibre is more deeply coloured than the upper one. It was thought that the higher percentage of lignin was the cause. The jute was therefore cut into three equal portions, purified in the usual way and lignin was estimated by hydrochloric acid method (*Ber.*, 1913, 46, 2401) in each portion. The percentages were 15·38, 15·40, 15·41 showing that lignin was homogeneously distributed along the fibre. This fact lends some support to the theory that in lignocelluloses lignin is chemically combined with cellulose.

The ash has been subsequently found to accompany tenaciously the lignin isolated by acid hydrolysis; it was therefore qualitatively analysed and the following metals have been detected in the same, *viz.*, Mg, Ca, Fe, and Al; silica has also been found. The presence of some of these at least, *e.g.*, Ca and Mg might be attributed to the pectin present in jute. It was therefore attempted to remove the pectin first without isolating lignin. 0·5 Per cent ammoniumoxalate is a very good solvent for pectin and it has been shown by Chowdhury and Mitra (in a paper to be shortly published) from this laboratory, that pectin can be quantitatively removed by two extractions with ammonium oxalate from jute completely delignified by chlorine peroxide. But in the case of raw jute, only a small amount of pectin could thus be extracted by the present investigator even by ten repeated extractions. It appears quite probable that lignin serve as a protective coating—which is impervious to ammonium oxalate. A pectin-lignin combination does not seem to be probable inasmuch as lignin alone and no pectin has been found to be present in various timbers (*Ritter, Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1925, 17, 1194).

As pectin has been found to be readily hydrolysable by acids, its presence cannot interfere with the estimation of lignin by the acid process. The metallic radicals in that case give salts soluble in water. So lignin was estimated without removing pectin beforehand. Hemi-celluloses are also very readily hydrolysed to water-soluble sugars on boiling with dilute acids and so it was unnecessary to remove them previously by 5 per cent. caustic soda in the cold.

Extractions with various other neutral solvents for the isolation of free lignin was found to be quite useless. The lignocellulose had to be hydrolysed either by acids or alkalis in order to obtain the lignin. There are at present altogether five different methods for the estimation of lignin, *viz.*, (a) by caustic soda under pressure, (b) by 42 per cent. hydrochloric acid at ordinary temperature, (c) by

72 per cent. sulphuric acid, (d) by 2 per cent. aqueous alcoholic caustic soda and (e) by hydrochloric acid and phosphorus pentoxide. All these methods have been tried one after another in the case of jute—they are described in detail in the following paragraphs.

(a) *By Caustic Soda under Pressure.*—In her studies on lignification Mehta (*loc. cit.*) investigated thoroughly the alkali process for the isolation of lignin and found that treatment with 4 per cent. caustic soda under 10 atmosphere pressure (185°) was the best method for the estimation of lignin in timbers. She considered that lignin isolated by this process suffered no internal change whatsoever, it was homogeneous and the resolution was complete in one hour. But the yield of lignin was in all cases lower than that by acid processes. It differed from all lignins described previously in that it was soluble in fairly large number of organic solvents, and had a definite melting point. The method at first sight appeared to yield a lignin in more or less pure form and was therefore tried first of all.

5 G. of finely cut purified jute were taken in a glass vessel, mixed with 100 c.c. of 4% caustic soda and heated in an autoclave at 185°, under 10 atmosphere pressure for one hour. The contents were then cooled, filtered to a measuring flask and the residual cellulose washed with water until the washings were colourless. The volume was made up to 250 c.c. Fifty c.c. of the deep brown liquor were taken in a beaker, and the lignin was precipitated by adding sufficient strong hydrochloric acid. The precipitate was allowed to settle, filtered through an ordinary filter paper, and washed until the washings were free from chloride (silver nitrate test). The washings were always light brown, indicating that the substance was partly soluble in water. By washing with hot water, a filtrate of deeper colour was obtained; it being more soluble in hot water. Lignin was then purified by dissolving in 95 p. c. boiling alcohol and evaporating off the solvent subsequently on water-bath. It was dried at 110° and weighed. The yield was never concordant; it varied between 2.7 and 3.4 per cent. depending upon the number of washings with water. The figure is too low to be accepted, as the percentage of lignin in jute has been previously found to be about 15 p. c. by chlorine peroxide method and by the method of Willstätter and Zechmeister (*Ber.*, 1913, **46**, 2401).

Lignin obviously suffered decomposition so as to give water-soluble products. It might be due to the concentration of the

alkali and the high pressure employed. The resolution of lignin was then carried out with 1% alkali and under 5 atmosphere pressure. The percentage was about 4.4, but the resolution was never complete; lignin could be further obtained from the residual cellulose by the acid process. The lignin, as before was partially soluble in water. The drawback of this process has also been recently shown by Dorée and Barton-Wright (*Biochem. J.*, 1927, 21, 290) who following strictly Mehta's method, could obtain only 18.6 p. c. lignin, 7.3 p. c. being soluble in water and 3.7% remaining with the cellulose, making a total of 29.6%. They obtained a simpler product ($C_{20}H_{20}O_6$) having a fixed melting point, and named it "meta-lignin". As my primary concern was to obtain lignin from jute in the form in which it exists in jute, this method had to be abandoned. But it is interesting to note here that the "lignin" obtained from jute does not melt below 300° ; it is a deep brown amorphous substance, obtained as a glistening solid on the evaporation of alcohol. It is soluble in glacial acetic acid, pyridine, acetone, aniline, in the cold; but insoluble in benzene, ether, carbon disulphide, carbon tetrachloride and slightly soluble in boiling nitrobenzene and chloroform. No trace of sodium could be found in the lignin showing that sodium has not entered the lignin molecule. It gives no ash. It reduces Fehling's solution quite readily. With chlorine in carbon tetrachloride suspension, a deep yellow product is obtained, hydrochloric acid being simultaneously evolved; substitution evidently, takes place. It has no aromatic odour like vanillin. It gives no furfural showing the absence of pentosans. But it gives a small amount of carbon dioxide when distilled with 12 p. c. hydrochloric acid, showing perhaps the presence of a carboxyl group, part of which might have been lost during isolation, as otherwise it is difficult to explain the evolution of carbon dioxide. It gives 20.1 p. c. methoxy (by Zeisel's method). An acetyl compound is readily obtained with acetic anhydride and a few drops of strong sulphuric acid, at 80° , showing the presence of hydroxyl groups.

(b) *Hydrochloric Acid Process*.—The use of fuming hydrochloric acid (42 p. c. in the isolation of lignin from ligno-celluloses was first proposed by Willstätter and Zechmeister (*loc. cit.*) and this method has been employed more than any other for the determination of lignin by many investigators during the last few years. The following procedure was adopted for the estimation of lignin from jute.

42 p. c. Hydrochloric acid (d 1.21) cannot be obtained in the market. Passing hydrochloric acid gas into jute suspended in strong hydrochloric acid cooled in ice, was found quite unsatisfactory. The following method was, however, found suitable.

Dry hydrochloric acid gas was passed into Merck's fuming hydrochloric acid (d 1.175) contained in a gas-washer which was cooled with ice and common salt until the density rose up to 1.21. One g. of very finely cut jute (of known moisture content) was taken in a well fitted glass stoppered bottle (250 c.c.), 50 c.c. of the prepared hydrochloric acid were quickly introduced and the stoppered bottle was shaken vigorously for about 15 mins. holding the stopper tightly. The stopper was kept under pressure so that the hydrochloric acid gas might not escape. Twelve hours at room temperature were found to be quite sufficient for the acid to dissolve the cellulose completely. The lignin obtained is deep black instead of light grey if the exposure be prolonged. It is important to note here that 40 p. c. hydrochloric acid does not dissolve the cellulose completely even when it is allowed to act for 48 hours. Traces of jute taken remain undissolved even with 42 p. c. hydrochloric acid if not shaken occasionally. The whole was then poured into a large volume of water and the contents of the bottle washed off into the beaker. The acid was diluted to about 7-8 p. c. and the whole boiled for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. There is considerable difficulty in filtering the lignin owing to the colloidal nature of the solution, if this last operation is omitted. It was filtered hot through asbestos in a Gooch crucible, washed repeatedly with boiling water until the washings were neutral to litmus. It was then dried at 110° and weighed. The results obtained are fairly concordant, the mean value being 15.43 p. c. (calculated on dry jute).

The lignin was obtained as a light spongy mass of grey colour. In order to determine the percentage of undissolved cellulose if any, a weighed quantity of finely powdered lignin was suspended in water in a gas washer and chlorine peroxide gas was passed through the washer, for about 16 hours. The lignin was dissolved by the chlorine peroxide. The whole was filtered through a glass filter, dried at 110° and weighed. The residue amounted to 0.13 p. c. But this was not cellulose, as most of it dissolved in strong hydrochloric acid and Ca, Mg, and Fe were detected in the solution. The rest was silica. Thus it must be attributed to the ash-giving bodies present in lignin; and not to any undissolved cellulose.

The lignin gives no furfural showing the absence of pentosans. It does not melt below 300° and is insoluble in all organic solvents. It is very slightly soluble in caustic soda, pyridine and ammonia. It gives 0.13 p. c. ash and 16.4 p. c. methoxy (Zeisel). It also gives carbon dioxide (1.557) when distilled with 12 p. c. hydrochloric acid and reduces Fehling's solution readily and gives a yellow chloro-derivative, with the evolution of hydrochloric acid when chlorine is passed in carbon tetrachloride suspension. The chloro-lignin is soluble in dilute alkalis, alcohol, pyridine, acetone, it does not melt below 300° and reduces Fehling's solution. It contains 27.87 p. c. chlorine (Carius). This lignin is readily oxidised by alkaline hydrogen peroxide and strong nitric acid to water-soluble products.

Attempts to acetylate this lignin with acetic anhydride and strong sulphuric acid, or sodium acetate (anhydrous), with acetyl chloride alone, and with pyridine were only partially successful as only a small yield of acetyl compound was obtained. Better results were obtained by prolonged heating with acetic anhydride and zinc chloride under reflux at $130-40^{\circ}$. The acetyl lignin (5.78 p. c. acetyl, Perkin's method) is a deep brown amorphous substance, soluble in pyridine, alkalis and glacial acetic acid but insoluble in sodium carbonate solution.

It was difficult to remove the last trace of hydrochloric acid from the lignin—the aqueous washings were neutral to litmus but gave test for chloride with silver nitrate. The mass being spongy a small amount of hydrochloric acid was tenaciously retained by it and only repeated treatment with boiling water under reflux, could effect complete removal. The comparatively higher values obtained by Willstätter process are often ascribed to the combination of lignin with hydrochloric acid; but the absence of chlorine in the lignin thus obtained does not support this view.

The lignin being insoluble in all media, it was not possible to purify it further. Lignin, if it be purely an organic compound, should give no ash. But it has not yet been possible to obtain ash-free lignin by acid hydrolysis. Phillips (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 2420) obtained a lignin from corn cobs by hydrochloric acid method, whose ash content was 1.05%. This ash must be due to the presence of impurities associated with the original ligno-cellulose or lignin itself is an organo-metallic compound. The former however, appears to be more probable in view of the fact that the percentage is too low, and that more than one metal have been detected in

the ash, which is never constant in percentage. Attempts are being made to remove these impurities so as to obtain lignin in the pure form suitable for ultimate analysis.

(c) *Sulphuric Acid Method*.—Probably the oldest and most commonly used method for the estimation of lignin is due to Klason (*Ber. der Vereins der Papier u. Zellstoffchemiker*, 1908, pp. 52-53) who hydrolysed finely divided wood with 70% sulphuric acid at room temperature. The polysaccharides dissolved and lignin remained insoluble. König (Dissertation, 1914, Munster) modified this method by recommending the use of 72% sulphuric acid. Lignin from jute was estimated in the following way:

1 G. of finely cut jute was treated with 25 c.c. of 72% sulphuric acid in a stoppered bottle, and the two were intimately mixed with a glass rod causing the jute to become completely disintegrated. The bottle was shaken occasionally and kept at room temperature for 16 hours, after which the acid was diluted with water to about 3%, boiled for half an hour and filtered hot through a Gooch crucible. The precipitate was washed free from acid by hot water, dried at 110° and weighed. Filtration even after boiling was very tedious: repeated washings with hot water for two days were required to make it acid-free. The yield was 18.2% (calculated on dry jute).

The lignin obtained is a very pasty deep black mass, which on drying gives a heavy solid, difficult to powder. Like the hydrochloric acid lignin, it is insoluble in all common solvents and alkalis. It does not melt even at 300°. It gives 0.31% ash, 13.5% methoxy, contains no sulphur, reduces Fehling's solution, gives carbon dioxide on distillation with 12% hydrochloric acid, but no furfural. Only partial acetylation could be effected by acetic anhydride and zinc chloride. It contains no undissolved cellulose. When heated under 10 atmosphere pressure with 4% caustic soda for one hour it dissolved in the alkali and gave a precipitate with hydrochloric acid which is slightly soluble in water. In other respects also it is identical with the alkali lignin. With chlorine in carbon tetrachloride a yellow chloro-derivative is obtained.

(d) *Alcoholic Caustic Soda Process*.—Beckmann, Liesche and Lehmann (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1921, 34, 285) employed 2% caustic soda in aqueous alcoholic solution acting in the cold for 48 hours for the isolation of lignin from rye straw. The alcohol prevented the solution of hemi-celluloses, pentosans and other non-lignified substances soluble in aqueous alkali. In the case of jute, 50 g. of finely cut jute

were treated with 250 c.c. of 2% alcoholic caustic soda (5 g. caustic soda, 100 c.c. water and 150 c.c. alcohol-95%) and allowed to stand at room temperature for 24 hours. The filtered solution was neutralised with hydrochloric acid and alcohol was distilled off under reduced pressure. The aqueous solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid and the precipitated lignin was filtered off. There was considerable difficulty in filtration due to the colloidal nature of the lignin. The yield was very poor being only 1.3%. By a second treatment a further yield of 0.6% was obtained. It is a light yellow powder, soluble in alcohol. Least drastic though the conditions of isolation, obviously it cannot be employed for the quantitative estimation of lignin. It was therefore discarded.

(e) *With Hydrochloric Acid and Phosphorus Pentoxide.*—Wenzl (*Papierfabr.*, 1924, 22, 101) employed fuming hydrochloric acid (d 1.19) mixed with phosphorus pentoxide for the estimation of lignin. 30 G. of the oxide were gradually added to 100 c.c. of the acid while cooling in ice. 1 G. of jute was digested with 25 c.c. of this mixture for 16 hours at room temperature in a stoppered phial. The solution was then diluted with water, boiled for about half an hour, filtered and the lignin dried and weighed. The yield and physical and chemical properties are all similar to the hydrochloric acid lignin. In fact, it is no new method and the results obtained are not different.

Of all the five methods tried for the isolation and estimation of lignin from jute, Willstätter's method was found to be the best. In the sulphuric acid process, the higher yield has been ascribed to the formation of humus (Paloheimo, *Biochem. Z.*, 1925, 165, 463) and to the absorption by lignin of secondary products. The percentage of methoxy is lower, a fraction of the methoxy groups has been lost in the process of isolation. The ash content is lower in the hydrochloric acid process (0.13%) than in the sulphuric acid process (0.31%). The estimation of lignin by difference with chlorine peroxide which has been shown by Chowdhury and Majumdar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 239) to have almost no effect on other constituents of jute, give the figure, 15.2% (obtained by the present worker) which is in close agreement with that obtained by the hydrochloric acid process.

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